

Field trials of information fusion, expert reasoning, social media exploitation and worksite operations in SAR missions – INGENIOUS* (EU Horizon 2020)

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ABSTRACT

On September 29th, 2021 a field testing activity for the INGENIOUS project took place at HRTA's training facilities in Afidnes (ATC), Attica region of Greece. The INGENIOUS project is about ensuring a high level of protection and augmented operational capacity for First Responders (FR) working inside the disaster area. The main objectives of these two Small Scale Field Tests included the integration of the specific components of the INGENIOUS Toolkit in real-life conditions, in order to provide testing, assessment, validation and improvements for further development steps. FRs have a significant role as they are the end-users that in future will depend on technologies like these, while robustness, accuracy and reliability of the components are crucial acceptance factors. Hence, this work presents these field tests, their outcomes and the assessment of their results from the FR perspective for real-world Search and Rescue (SAR) operations.

Keywords: Search and Rescue, field tests, crisis management, security and safety, First responders

1. INTRODUCTION

Search & Rescue (SAR) operations require a high level of training, skills, team capacity and safety procedures. Newly developed tools and technologies can enhance the operational capabilities of First Responders (FRs) in such missions, especially with regard to rapid response in continuously changing environments. The INGENIOUS project (EU Horizon 2020) aims at developing, integrating, testing and validating a next generation SAR toolkit for collaborative team response, providing enhanced protection and augmented operational capabilities.

One of the most crucial factors for the successful development and adoption of novel technologies by FRs in existing SAR operational protocols and guidelines is the active, early involvement of the actual end-users. Instead of providing them with completed prototypes to test and assess for the first time in the field, an iterative collaborative approach is much more effective and risk-preventive in terms of developing tools that are operationally unfit or incompatible with the FR expectancies.

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For these reasons, a series of iterative laboratory and field tests have been planned throughout the INGENIOUS project, involving individual tools as well as integration cycles, where FR operators can test, evaluate and comment on the progress of the development from very early on. In this context, Small Scale Field Tests SST#7 and SST#8 were organized and conducted during September 2021 at the Afidnes Training Center (ATC) in Athens, Greece, under the coordination of the Hellenic Rescue Team of Attica (HRTA) as the corresponding end-user in the project consortium.

2. METHODOLOGY – DESCRIPTION OF THE FIELD TRIALS

Four main components were selected from the Next Generation Integrated Toolkit (NGIT) of the INGENIOUS project to be tested and evaluated in this set of field activities:

- **Fusion Engine (FE):** Data gathering, fusion and combined feeds to other components in NGIT.
- **Expert Reasoning Engine (ERE):** Information fusion, assessment, mission-critical and safety-critical alerting during the operations.
- **Worksite Operations Application (WOA):** Integrated coordination platform for mission Command & Control (C&C) at the team level, as well as the Urban Coordination Cell (UCC).
- **Social Media Application (SMA):** Online monitoring of social media platforms for prompt alerting regarding possible large-scale disaster events as they are evolving.

From the technical partners of the consortium, EXUS and CERTH are the developers of Fusion Engine (FE) & Expert Reasoning Engine (ERE), Worksite Operations App (WOA) (EXUS) and Social Media App (CERTH), while from FRs' side HRTA and ERTZ were present as end-users and field testers. The tested components of the NGIT for Collaborative Response were presented by the technical partners and FRs interacted during the event with a mixed team from Greece and Spain.

The components that were demonstrated/tested during SST#7 included the Fusion Engine (FE), the Expert Reasoning Engine (ERE) and the Worksite Operations App (WOA). The use case that was used involved first response in a single site after a terror attack in public space, as it was defined at previous stages of the project. Similarly, SST#8 focused on the demonstration and field testing of the Social Media App (SMA) component.

2.1. Fusion Engine

The Fusion Engine was tested with incoming data received by the present components (either physically present or remote) and by data generators to replicate the input from components where data were not yet available. Several scenarios and conditions were tested. Functionalities that were tested included interoperability with components, registration of resources, FR Health Status early warning, Danger Zone Rating, among others.

2.2. Expert Reasoning Engine (ERE)

The Expert Reasoning Engine (ERE) was tested in terms of health status warnings and the detection of abnormalities and communication with the Common Operational Picture Platform (COP) through alerts that feature the status the severity or the urgency of an incident. Within the scenario, there was a need to monitor the health status of the First Responders. To tackle this, the Expert Reasoning component receives the measurements of the vitals and processes them for detecting abnormalities. These

abnormalities in the measurements can be the results of dehydration, exhaustion and heatstroke. As a result, the component pushes the corresponding alerts to the COP to monitor the health status of the First Responder.

At this stage, the knowledge base of the module was implemented regarding the FR's status. Each person contains entities that are possible to be impacted by the crisis (Figure 1). The result of the impact is visible through the vital signs (body temperature, blood oxygen level, heart rate, etc) that are measured by the other components, and lead to the physiological condition (tiredness, asymmetric waking etc).

Figure 1. FR status and impact analysis (ERE).

2.3. Worksite Operations Application (WOA)

The Worksite Operations App (WOA) demonstrated functionalities regarding the resource management, decision support and system integration with FE and other online resources. More specifically, the WOA component plays a vital role in coordinating FR teams at the worksite level, monitoring assets and deployment locations, while at the top-level C&C it functions as the workbench for the coordination of multiple teams and guidance from the UCC.

2.4. Social Media Application (SMA)

During large-scale disaster events like in wildfires, people in the affected region used to post on social media to learn and inform about critical information about the fires. In addition, FR teams can use this information to their advantage. As a result, the Social Media App aims to collect the related information and filter out the irrelevant in real-time by detecting events related to a simulated large forest fire near residential areas.

During the SST#8, real tweets were posted, in real-time, on the Twitter platform. As Twitter is a public platform, those tweets were encoded with particular hashtags and codes to avoid false alerts to the platform's users (Figure 2). The new upcoming tweets are stored and processed near-real time by the appropriate services. Then, the event detection method collected and grouped the relevant tweets based on the time posted and the location. In particular, each group of tweets refers to an event detection message. The corresponding events with the post analysis information were sent from FE to COP in order to be monitored in the COP platform.

	A	B
39		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Καίγονται οπίσθια σε BR940 και AD967 - Η πυρκαγιά πήρασε το RIM543 - Έχει διακοπή η κυκλοφορία στην ευρύτερη περιοχή - Έως
40		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Μαίνεται η μεγάλη πυρκαγιά στη BR940. Βίντεο: Κωνσταντίνος Πουλής
41		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Μαίνεται η πυρκαγιά στη BR940 – Ειδοποίηση από το 112 – Έκλεισε η εθνική οδός EO123 δείτε περισσότερα 📹
42		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Μαίνεται η πυρκαγιά στη BR940: Ειδοποίηση στους κατοίκους να κλείσουν πόρτες και παράθυρα – Διακοπές στην κυκλοφορία
43		irrelevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Απευρότητα θαυμασμός, στήριξη και κουράγιο στους ανθρώπους που κλέβονται από τις φωνικές πυρκαγιές και στους π
44		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Προς την Εθνική Οδό η πυρκαγιά στη BR940 - Δεν αποκλείει η Τροχαία την απογόρευση διέλευσης
45	Bunch 2	relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Πίσω από τσίχλες στο ρεύμα ελατώς ζημιές από την πυρκαγιά στη BR940 - ΔΕΔΗΕ: Πού θα σημειωθούν σήμερα διακοπές ρεύματος
46		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Πυρκαγιά στην Εθνική Οδό έχουν κλείσει το λεκανοπέδιο της ΑΤ845 από τη μεγάλη πυρκαγιά της BR940ς. Οι καρμικές συνθήκες δυσχεραίν
47		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Πυρκαγιά BR940: Εκκενώθηκε καταστήματα με 80 παιδιά- Κυκλοφοριακές ρυθμίσεις στην Εθνική Οδό
48		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Πυρκαγιά στη BR940: Δραματική η κατάσταση - Μήνυμα από το 112 – Χωρίς ρεύμα παραχές της ΑΤ845
49		irrelevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Μια από τις συνέπειες της κλιματικής αλλαγής είναι ότι οι πυρκαγιές θα γίνονται όλο και πιο πολλές, όλο και
50		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Πυρκαγιά στην BR940: Πού έχει διακοπή η κυκλοφορία των οχημάτων
51		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Σε εξέλιξη είναι η πυρκαγιά σε δασική έκταση στην BR940, όπου οι ισχυρές πυροβλαστικές δυνάμεις δίνουν μάχη για να περιορί
52		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Σε εξέλιξη η πυρκαγιά στη BR940 – Κλήση από το 112, διακοπές κυκλοφορίας -
53		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Σε εξέλιξη πυρκαγιά στη BR940
54		irrelevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Όμοια αδιέξοδα βέβαια έχει παραστεί από τη πυρκαγιά μπορεί να λάβει τις απαραίτητες πρώτες βοήθειες στο νοσοκομείο
55		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Σε εξέλιξη πυρκαγιά στη BR940 – Επικραούν ισχυρές δυνάμεις (βίντεο & φωτο)
56		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Στην πυρκαγιά στην δασική έκταση στην περιοχή UB345, του δόμου ΑΝ560 επιχειρούν 104 πυροσβέστες, με 4 ομάδες πεζοπόρου
57		irrelevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Φραγκοσκιά: Το φυτό που μπορεί να σταματήσει μια πυρκαγιά
58		relevant #THIS_IS_A_TEST #ingenioustest Φυριά - Επέγινε SMS από 112 στην μεγάλη πυρκαγιά που μαίνεται στην BR940 - Στα ΚΡ128

Figure 2. Examples used in training the event-detection model (SMA).

3. CONCLUSIONS

SST#7 and SST#8 were the first opportunity for Small Scale Field Tests of the FE, ERE, WOA and SMA components. Although there were several setbacks, e.g. COVID-19 and fires affecting the HRTA location, these field tests were conducted successfully and with overall positive feedback from the end users. The functionalities demonstrated by all three components (FE, ERE, WOA, SMA) satisfied the technical requirements that were established by the technical partners and end users, such as location information of victims, FRs, and incidents, allow FRs to select areas and display information, raise alarms regarding the physical state of FRs among others.

The impression FRs gained is that the overall development of these technologies is on track, although it needs further development and some minor changes in order to be operationally usable. Based on the FR comments, the Fusion Engine & Expert Reasoning, as well as the Social Media App, can be included in the standard FR tools in the field, helping in gathering information and enhancing the situational awareness, as well as protecting them from unseen hazards.

Further information collected through the formal evaluation, but also through the experience of field deployment led to additional improvements of the components. Specifically, the next steps will include:

- Provide to COP info on hover of rated zones (type of gas, concentration, etc).
- WOA to show points of interest in map (such as camp, fuel station, etc)
- Continuous integration with other components of the NGIT

Also, special attention will be given to improving the security of the developed solutions and focusing on the collection and application of real time data.

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